

GEOBOTANICAL STUDIES OF THE DESERT ZONES OF THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN, IN PARTICULAR, THE KYZYLKUM DESERT

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Abstract: *This article discusses the issues of Kyzylkum Desert and the geobotanical researches we conducted in order to study the current state of vegetation cover in this area. In particular, pastures with the participation of tytra and tasbiyurgun. Also, in this article, we will talk about the study of the anthropogenic effect on the vegetation of arid regions and the application of agrotechnical methods for the phytoremediation of low-yielding pastures.*

Key words: *Kyzylkum desert, phytoremediation, xeromorphism, plant cover, association, slightly sandy gypsum soil.*

INTRODUCTION

The Kyzyl Kum desert is one of the most important grazing lands for Karakul sheep, camels and plays an important role in the development of transhumance in the Republic. It is characterized by very low and extremely unstable yields. Since there are sharp fluctuations in daily temperatures, summer daytime heat is often replaced by cool winds, in winter night frosts are replaced by daytime thaws. The listed features of the climate have developed the ability of plants: a period of heat cover in the summer months, a shift in the development cycle in the spring-summer period; xeromorphism of structures, the predominance of life forms, such as semi-shrub, semi-shrub, ephemeroïd, perennial herbs, long-term vegetative saltwort, annuals, etc. [2]. In such xerothermic desert conditions, the flora of Kyzylkum was formed, which, according to a preliminary calculation, consists of about 1050 species and is widely distributed on various soil varieties. Pastures with the

participation of shrubs, semi-shrubs and semi-shrubs, for example: with wormwood, tytr, tasbiyurgun.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

We carried out geobotanical studies to study the current state of the vegetation cover in this region. In particular; pastures with the participation of tytra and tasbiyurgun. The yield is not high up to 0.5-1.0 (1.5) c/ha, here the vegetation is very sparse, the projective cover is not high, in some areas it is 25-30%. Therefore, the study of the species and age composition, productivity, life forms of the titer and tasbiyurgun communities is of great importance in animal husbandry, as well as in the study of the impact of the anthropogenic factor on the vegetation of arid regions and the use of agrotechnical methods for the purpose of phytomelioration of low-yielding pastures [1,2,4,5 , eight].

DISCUSSION

Vegetation cover studies in the Southwestern Kyzylkum were started according to the above methods, and a number of associations of tytra and tasbiyurgun communities of tytra formations were described. According to edaphic conditions, they are classified as pelitohalophytes [1]. When compiling “Phytomeliorative map of Southern Kyzylkum” the author of this article also described communities of the tytra formation, which included 9 associations developed on compacted gray-brown saline, heavy loamy soils (Mutalov, 1986, 1989) [5,6,7,8,9].

In the South-Western Kyzyl Kum, among semishrubs tytr - (*Salsola gemmasces*) and tasbiyurgun - (*Nanaphiton erinaceum*) is found relatively on leveled heavy loamy and clayey soils of residual solonchaks. Their growing season is from early April to mid-October. Flowering from late May to late June. Fruiting lasts from June to October.

The communities of the tytra formation are distributed on the alluvial plains of the Murgab and Tejen rivers [12], along the piedmont plains of the Kopet-Dag on the Ustyurt Plateau, and in Southwestern Kyzylkum.

Tytr (*S.gemmscens*) participates in the formation of various communities developed on compacted gray-brown saline soils with tasbiyurgun, and on weakly sandy gypsum-bearing soil with syngren, bolylysh and wormwood. Issues of biology, flowering, fruiting and embryogenesis of tytra have been studied, - phytocenotic diversity, N.I. Akzhigitova (1973), I.F. Momotov (1973) and others. Tytr-haloxerophytic, semishrub 15-35 cm tall. Vegetation begins at the end of March and ends at the end of November. Tytr is confined to heavy loamy and clayey residual solonchaks and gravel-loamy gypsum-bearing and takyr soils, therefore N.I.Akzhigitova refers to pelitophyte plants. Accompanying in the titer communities is a hidden carp (*Camanthus gomokarpus*), biyurgun (*Anabasis salsa*), cryptodiscus (*Prangos ammophyla*), buzavbash (*Halimoknemis longifolia*), Girgenzonia (*Girgensohnia oppositiflora*).

In southern Kyzylkum, the community of the titer formation is represented by the following associations: titer, tasbiyurgun-tytra, wormwood-titra, keireuk-wormwood-titra, keireuk-tasbiyurgun-titra, sparsely keireuk-tytra. In this formation, we described 9 associations of this formation. As an example, we give a characteristic area of the keireuk-wormwood-tytra association developed on takyr-like soil, the surface of which is covered in places with fine gravel, slightly sandy along the edges of the takyr on May 22, 1980, 1.5 km north of the Aldayarzhiga well.

The titer formation as a whole is characterized by sparseness and poverty of the species composition. In the composition of the species composition: from shrubs there is a single boyalysh - (*Salsola arbuscula*) from semi-shrubs tasbiyurgun - (*Nanafiton erinaceum*), keireuk - (*Salsola orientais*), chogon - (*Aelleynia subafilla*) from annual donashur saltworts - (*Halimocnemis Longifolia*), in spring period from

ephemeroids *ferula* - (*Ferula foetida*), *ilak* - (*Carex phesodes*), from saltworts are found - (*Gamanthus gamocarpus*, *Girgesonia oppositiflora*, *H. longifolia*.) In most cases, their projective cover does not exceed 20%, - also accounts for the share of participation ephemers and ephemeroids which are mainly confined to slightly lowered sandy places. [2.7.8].

The *Tasbiyurgun-tytra* association (*Salsola gemmascens*- *Nanopheton erinaceum*) is characteristic of the southern Kyzylkum for a weakly expressed southern piedmont mountain plain. *Kuldzhuktau*, especially in the area of the dry *Daryasay* riverbed. The soil is gray-brown, loamy, its strongly compacted surface is covered with rubble. Plot (46) was described jointly with I.F. Momotov (April 13, 1977) 12 km south of *Kol. Tashkuduk*. Vegetation cover is complex. The described *tasbiyurgun-titer* community is distributed on a compacted gravelly leveled area, where the soil is covered with vegetation by 15% and the territory without vegetation, occupies up to 80%. in some places on weakly expressed sandy depressions due to silt, the projective cover is 35%.

Chogon - (*Aellenia subaphilla*) forms the first tier of the association, *tasbiyurgun* and *tytr*-second tier, and the third - ephemeroids and ephemera.

Plot 11, described on April 25, 1977, on the dry channel of the *Daryasai*, is characteristic of the *keireuk-tytra* association (*S. gemmascens*-*S. orientalis*), the soil is *takyr*, saline, covered with a clay crust from the surface. The projective vegetation cover is 20-25%, the *takyr* itself occupies 40% of the area. The following are registered on the site: *Artemisia turanica*, *Salsola orientalis*, *S. gemmascens*, *Gamanthus gamocarpus*, 7 species in total.

CONCLUSION

As a result of ongoing geobotanical studies to study the current state of the vegetation cover of this region, we have described associations of the *tytra* formation with the participation of *boylysh*, *wormwood*, *keireuk* and *chogon*. With an increase in the load, a decrease in the number of ephemeroids is observed, and the

introduction of annuals and weedy species such as *Peganum garmala*, *Acanthophyllum pungens*, *Ceratocephalis falkata*: tytra, tasbiyurgun-tytra, wormwood-tytra, keireuk-wormwood-tytra, keireuk-tasbiyurgun-tytra, sparse-keireuk-tytra, all described associations belong to pelitohalophytes [1] are mainly formed on gypsum-bearing gray-brown compacted takyr and takyr-like saline soils, the surface of which is covered with fine multi-colored gravel.

As noted above, the yield of associations of this formation is low within 0.5-1.0 centner/ha due to singly occurring boyalish, chogon, as well as annual saltworts, ephemers and ephemeroids. In the program for the improvement of low-yielding and degraded pastures, titer formations must be included in the list of priority improvements for phytomelioration.

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